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IMPLEMENTATION OF A 8 BIT HIGH PERFORMANCE MULTIPLIER USING HDL

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Abstract

This paper presents an area efficient implementation of a 8 bit high performance parallel multiplier. Radix-8 Booth multiplier with carry look ahead adder and modified carry look ahead adder are presented here. The design is structured for 8 bit multiplication. Carry Look ahead Adder is used as the final adder to enhance the speed of operation. Finally the performance improvement of the proposed multipliers is validated by implementing a multiplier with modified carry look ahead adder. The design entry is done in Verilog and simulated using Model Sim SE 6.4 design suite from Mentor Graphics. It is then synthesized and implemented using Xilinx ISE 9.2i .

Keywords- HDL; Modified Carry Look-ahead Adder; Carry Save Adder; Wallace Tree; Booth Encoding.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid advances in multimedia and communication systems, real-time signal processing and large capacity data processing are increasingly being demanded. The multiplier is an essential element of the digital signal processing such as filtering and convolution. Most digital signal processing methods use nonlinear functions such as discrete cosine transform (DCT) or discrete wavelet transform (DWT). As they are basically accomplished by repetitive application of multiplication and addition, their speed becomes a major factor which determines the performance of the entire calculation. Since the multiplier requires the longest delay among the basic operational blocks in digital system, the critical path is determined more by the multiplier [1]. Furthermore, multiplier consumes much area and dissipates more power. Hence designing multipliers which offer either of the following design targets – high speed, low power consumption [2], less area or even a combination of them is of substantial research interest.

Multiplication operation involves generation of partial products and their accumulation. The speed of multiplication can be increased by reducing the number of partial products and/or accelerating the accumulation of partial products. Among the many methods of implementing high speed parallel multipliers, there are two basic approaches namely Booth algorithm and Wallace Tree compressors. This paper describes an efficient

implementation of a high speed parallel multiplier using both these approaches. Here two multipliers are proposed. The first multiplier makes use of the Radix-8

Booth Algorithm with carry look ahead adder while the second multiplier uses the Radix-8 Booth algorithm with modified carry look ahead adder as the final adders.

The design is structured for 8 bit multiplication. The number of partial products is $n/3$ in Radix-8 Booth algorithm. The Wallace tree uses Carry Save Adders (CSA) to accumulate the partial products. This reduces the time as well as the chip area. To further enhance the speed of operation, carry-look-ahead (CLA) adder is used as the final adder[3]. The multiplier is also implemented using modified carry look ahead adder as the final adder and the delay parameters are compared.

II. ARCHITECTURE

The architecture of the proposed multiplier is shown in Fig.1. It consists of four major modules: Booth encoder, partial product generator, Wallace tree and carry look-ahead adder[4]. The Booth encoder performs Radix-2 or Radix-4 or Radix-8 encoding of the multiplier bits. Based on the multiplicand and the encoded multiplier, partial products are generated by the generator. For large multipliers of 32 bits, the performance of the modified Booth algorithm is limited. So Booth recoding together with Wallace tree structures have been used in the proposed fast multiplier. The partial products are supplied to Wallace Tree and added appropriately. The results are finally added using a Modified Carry Look-ahead Adder (MCLA) and Modified Carry Look-ahead adder to get the final product.

Figure 1. Block diagram of Wallace Booth Multiplier

Booth algorithm is a powerful algorithm [5] for signed number multiplication, which treats both positive and negative numbers uniformly. Since a k -bit binary number can be interpreted as $k/2$ -digit Radix-4 number, a $k/3$ -digit Radix-8 number and so on, it can deal with more than one bit of the multiplier in each cycle by using high radix multiplication[6]. The major disadvantage of the Radix-2 algorithm was that the process required n shifts and an average of $n/2$ additions for an n bit multiplier. This variable number of shift and add operations is inconvenient for designing parallel multipliers. Also the Radix-2 algorithm becomes inefficient when there are isolated 1's. The Radix-4 modified Booth algorithm overcomes all these limitations of Radix-2 algorithm. For operands equal to or greater than 16 bits, the modified Radix-4 Booth algorithm has been widely used. It is based on encoding the two's complement multiplier in order to reduce the number of partial products to be added to $n/2$. The multiplier, Y in two's complement form can be written as in

$$Y = -Y_{n-1} 2^{n-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} Y_i 2^i \quad ; \quad 0 \leq i \leq n-2 \quad (1)$$

It can be written as

$$Y = \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} (-2 Y_{2i+1} + Y_{2i} + Y_{2i-1}) 2^{2i} \quad ; \quad 0 \leq i \leq n-2 \quad (2)$$

Table I shows the encoding of the signed multiplier Y, using the Radix-4 Booth algorithm. Radix-4 Booth recoding encodes multiplier bits into [-2, 2]. Here we consider the multiplier bits in blocks of three, such that each block overlaps the previous block by one bit. It is advantageous to begin the examination of the multiplier with the least significant bit. The overlap is necessary so that we know what happened in the last block, as the most significant bit of the block acts like a sign bit.

TABLE I. RADIX - 4 BOOTH RECODING

Multiplier Bits			Recoded Operation on multiplicand, X
Y _{2i-1}	Y _{2i}	Y _{2i+1}	
0	0	0	0X
0	0	1	+X
0	1	0	+X
0	1	1	+2X
1	0	0	-2X
1	0	1	-X
1	1	0	-X
1	1	1	0X

Radix-8 Booth recoding applies the same algorithm as that of Radix-4, but now we take quartets of bits instead of triplets. Each quartet is codified as a signed digit using Table II. Radix-8 algorithm reduces the number of partial products to n/3, where n is the number of multiplier bits. Thus it allows a time gain in the partial products summation.

C. Wallace Tree

The Wallace tree method [7] is used in high speed designs in order to produce two rows of partial products that can be added in the last stage. Also critical path and the number of adders get reduced when compared to the conventional parallel adders. Here the Wallace tree has taken the role of accelerating the accumulation of the partial products. Its advantage becomes more pronounced for multipliers of greater than 16 bits. The speed, area and power consumption of the multipliers will be in direct proportion to the efficiency of the compressors. The Wallace tree structure with 3:2 compressors is shown in Fig.2.

TABLE II. RADIX -8 BOOTH RECODING

Multiplier Bits $Y_{i+2} Y_{i+1} Y_i$	recoded Operation on multiplicand X
0 0 0 0	0X
0 0 0 1	+X
0 0 1 0	+X
0 0 1 1	+2X
0 1 0 0	+2X
0 1 0 1	+3X
0 1 1 0	+3X
0 1 1 1	+4X
1 0 0 0	-4X
1 0 0 1	-3X
1 0 1 0	-3X
1 0 1 1	-2X
1 1 0 0	-2X
1 1 0 1	-1X
1 1 1 0	-1X
1 1 1 1	0X

Figure 2. Wallace Tree using 3:2 compressors

Figure. 3. 16 bit Modified Carry Look-ahead Adder

The 3:2 compressors make use of a carry save adder .The carry save adder outputs two numbers of the same dimensions as the inputs, one is a sequence of partial sum bits and other is a sequence of carry bits. In carry save adder, the carry digit is taken from the right and passed to the left, just as in conventional addition; but the carry digit passed to the left is the result of the previous calculation and not the current one. So in each clock cycle, carries only have to move one step along and the clock can tick much faster. Also the carry-save adder produces all of its output values in parallel, and thus has the same delay as a single full-adder. The number of levels in the Wallace tree using 3:2 compressors can be approximately given as

$$\text{Number of levels} = \frac{\log (k / 2)}{\log (3 / 2)} \quad (3)$$

where k is the number of partial products. Table III shows the number of levels in the Wallace tree using 3:2 compressors for different number of partial products.

TABLE III. NUMBER OF LEVELS IN THE WALLACE TREE

Number of Partial Products,(k)	Number of Levels in the Wallace Tree
3	1
4	2
5 k 6	3
7 k 9	4
10 k 13	5
14 k 19	6
20 k 28	7
29 k 42	8
43 k 63	9

The final results obtained at the output of the Wallace tree are added using a Modified Carry Look-ahead Adder (MCLA) which is independent of the number of bits of the two operands. In Modified Carry Look-ahead Adder, for every bit the carry and sum outputs are independent of the previous bits and thus the rippling effect has completely been eliminated. The Modified Carry Look Ahead Adder is similar to that of Carry Look Ahead

Adder, expect that MCLA works only on NAND gates and NOT gates making it work at faster rate as compared with a normal Carry Look-ahead Adder. It works by creating two signals, propagate and generate for each bit position, based on whether a carry is propagated through from a less significant bit position, a carry is generated in that bit position, or if a carry is killed in that bit position.

C. Carry-Look ahead Adder (CLA)

A carry-look ahead adder (CLA) is a type of adder used in digital logic. A carry-look ahead adder improves speed by reducing the amount of time required to determine carry bits. It can be contrasted with the simpler, but usually slower, ripple carry adder for which the carry bit is calculated alongside the sum bit, and each bit must wait until the previous carry has been calculated to begin calculating its own result and carry bits. The carry-look ahead adder

calculates one or more carry bits before the sum, which reduces the wait time to calculate the result of the larger value bits.

D. Modified Carry Look Ahead Adder (MCLA)

The method to simplify CLA circuit is using a NAND gate and a NOT gate to replace the AND gate of the output bit G in the $4m-1$ -bit (previous level) CLA circuit when m is greater than 1, and then cancel its NOT gate with the NOT gate in the $4m$ -bit (present level) CLA. The new circuit is named as MCLA. Let $K=4$. For example, there are three NOT gates in the carry look ahead circuit of 16-bit CLA. If we move back the three NOT gates into 4-bit CLA and simplify it with another four NOT gates in the proposed carry look ahead circuit of 16-bit CLA, we can derive the simplest circuits of 4-bit and 16-bit MCLA, as shown in Figures respectively.

III. IMPLEMENTATION RESULTS

The design entry of 8 bit multipliers using Radix-8 Booth algorithm with carry look ahead adder and modified carry look ahead adder are done using verilog and simulated using Model Sim SE 6.4 design suite from Mentor Graphics. It is then synthesized and implemented in Xilinx ISE 14.7i design suite. Figure 4 presents a snapshot of simulation waveforms for 8 bit multiplier.

Sampling frequency	:	24 KHz
Pass band frequency	:	8 KHz
Stop band frequency	:	9 KHz
Pass band ripple	:	0.1 linear scale
Stop band attenuation	:	0.001 linear scale

TABLE IV. DEVICE UTILIZATION SUMMARY OF MULTIPLIERS

Logic Utilization (XC3S5000 fg1156 -4)	Radix-8 Booth Algorithm with Carry Look- ahead adder	Radix -8 Booth Algorithm with Modified Carry Look ahead adder
Number of four input LUTs	29,990	43,520
Number of occupied Slices	135	141
Number of bonded IOBs	30	30
Total equivalent gate count	205,470	271,881
JTAG Gate Count for IOBs	24,144	24,144
Maximum combinational path delay (ns)	448.270	448.082
Average Connection Delay (ns)	15.542	7.830
Maximum Pin Delay (ns)	27.603	20.171

Messages				
+ /unsigned_radix_8/i...	94	94		
+ /unsigned_radix_8/i...	50	50		
+ /unsigned radix 8/...	4700	4700		

Figure 4.1 Simulation of 8 ×8 bit multiplier

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the design and implementation of two high performance parallel multipliers is proposed. The first multiplier makes use of the Radix-8 Booth Algorithm with simple carry look ahead adder while the second multiplier uses the Radix-8 Booth algorithm with modified carry look ahead adder as final adders. The multiplier using Radix-8 Booth algorithm with modified cla shows more reduction in device utilization as compared to the multiplier using Radix-8 Booth algorithm with modified cla. Meanwhile the multiplier using Radix-8 Booth algorithm with modified carry look ahead adder is found to be faster than the other.

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